

CZU: 378.126:159.9

PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT OF GRADUATES' PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE EMPLOYMENT SITUATION

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The article analyses the problem of professional development of university graduates in the employment situation. An essential stage of individual's professional development is considered the job searching and the beginning of self-employment. The study indicates the possible ways of the response of university graduates in the employment situation, which depends on the level of development of professional reflection and the type of value attitude to the profession. The research substantiates the necessity of development of the programme of psychological support of professional development of the person in a situation of employment. The article determined the chief organisation theoretical approaches and principles of the psychological support form for university graduates employment.

Keywords: *professional development, professionalisation, employment situation, psychological support*

SUPPORTUL PSIHOLGIC ACORDAT ABSOLVENȚILOR INSTITUȚIILOR UNIVERSITARE ÎN PROCESUL DE ANGAJARE

Autorul analizează problema privind dezvoltarea profesională a absolvenților instituțiilor universitare în procesul de angajare la un loc de muncă. O etapă esențială în dezvoltarea profesională poate fi considerată etapa de căutare a unui loc de muncă și consolidarea unui nou statut, a celui de angajat. Sunt evidențiate posibile tipuri de conduită a absolvenților în procesul de angajare care sunt direct relaționate de gradul de dezvoltare a capacității de reflecție profesională și de atitudinea față de profesie. Rezultatele cercetării demonstrează necesitatea elaborării unui program de suport psihologic al absolvenților aflați în căutarea unui loc de muncă. În acest sen, sunt analizate abordările teoretice de bază și principiile de organizare a unui training pentru asigurarea suportului psihologic al absolvenților în procesul de angajare.

Cuvinte-cheie: *dezvoltare profesională, profesionalizare, situație de angajare, suport psihologic.*

The relevance of research

At the present stage of development of the Ukrainian society, the issue of professional development of future specialists becomes especially relevant. In the context of globalization social processes, the professional development and elevating of young people involves not only receiving quality professional education in higher education, but also the formation of psychological readiness for professional mobility and creative self-development throughout life. The beginning stage of the independent professional activity of specialists allows perceiving the manner of optimal the professional choice and successful the process of professional self-determination (E.Golovakha, O.Golomshtok, O.Karpov, E.Klimov, M.Pryazhnikov and others). One of the factors of professional development of personality is the subjective employment strategy, the vector of which from adaptive to creative human activity determines the level of life and professional self-development of the specialist (K.Abulkhanova-Slavska, L.Bozhovych, M.Ginzburg, V.Krutetsky, S.Rubinstein). Many scientists determined the success of professionalisation and professional development by the level of development of the subjective activity of the specialist, the rank of his professional reflection, the ability to solve problems and constructively overcome normative and non-normative crises of professional development (V.Bodrov, E.Zeyer, E.Simanyuk, T.Kudryavtsev, A.Markova, L.Mitina, V.Shegurova and others).

The analysis of research and publications that have begun to solve the problem

For university graduates, the job search situation is primarily a life situation, which marks the beginning of a new stage of personal development, which opens up new professional prospects and opportunities for the person. According to B. Ananieva, the start of independent professional activity marks the transition of a person from a state of "being the object of educational influences" to a state of "being a subject of self-education and self-determination" [1]. However, the employment process can be a problematic situation, which depends on many objective and subjective factors.

The job search process can be quite a successful project, provided good professional training, social demand for the speciality, as well as high motivation and well-developed employment strategy. The crucial point is to

maintain a balance between goals, values, and aspirations of the specialist, and the realities of the modern labour market. Alongside, they will have to overcome the obstacles of the present-day labour market to be in the process of finding a job. The employment situation for today's graduates can be problematic, as job search has several factors which complicate it: high competition for the vacancy, lack of experience, lack of work skills, lack of employment, inability to write a CV, lack of interview skills and initiative. Thus, the success of university graduates' employment depends on many factors: including the ratio of adaptive and creative trends in the development of the subject of professional activity, the level of professional self-determination, which at the end of training acquires qualitatively new features, compared to self-determination of high school students.

During the crisis experiencing of the graduate (E.Zeyer, E.Symanyuk), the internal process of professional self-determination determines the quality and outcome of the university graduates employment. According to A.K. Osnytsky, already during higher education, professional self-determination turns into a process of consistent and focused assessment of themselves and their capabilities in the chosen profession and the inclusion of everything related to it in the structure of life plans. Under such conditions, a graduate of construction specialities is likely to look for a job in the speciality area, assessing the complexity of professional responsibilities following their abilities and skills [2].

The quality of the employment process also depends on the development of professional reflection. Researchers determine the different direction of reflection: the object of activity, the means of performing occupations, the way of existence of the subject of activity [3]. The last type of reflection characterises the ability of the subject (person) of professional activity to exercise value-semantic self-determination, which involves the next formulation and resolution of professional choices and determines the choice of place of work in the speciality or not.

Also, the graduates' attitude to the employment situation is associated with the process of becoming a subject of professional activity. Thus, the studies of T.V. Kudryavtseva show that the development of personality in the educational and professional activities determines a new attitude towards oneself. And this forces a person to reconsider the previously made professional choice [4]. In the employment situation, there is either a search for new arguments in favour of the already chosen profession or the choice of another non-professional sphere of self-realisation, in this context.

The aim and objectives of the study

The article aims to analyse the attitude of graduates of higher educational institutions to the employment situation depending on the level of development of professional reflection. The objectives of the study are to substantiate the job training form as psychological support for professional development in the employment situation.

Presenting the main material

In our opinion, the need for employment for today's graduates of higher educational institutions is the life situation that objectifies the personal ability to self-development in work and the level of professional reflection formed during the academic and professional activities. Depending on the level of development of reflection and capacity to self-determination, today's university graduates may show different attitudes to the employment situation: passive desire to find a job, active actions to find a job, creativity in search of their professional self-realisation.

The goal and wish to carry out such search activities outline the desire as the orientation of a person's activity in search of a work. The desire shows the need to experience, which turned into the productive thought to master a specific, personally-significant workplace. Thus, desire consciously determines the purpose of future actions. As a motive for activity, the awareness of the characteristics of the desired job quite clearly characterises the desire. A possible job requires not only its awareness but also the consideration of possible ways to get it. However, the graduate of the university in a state of desire strives to achieve the desired result. Moreover, if we exclude their independence and initiative, they'll have a poorly developed reflection.

In the employment situation, university graduates can take a more powerful position. In particular, it is an active conscious behaviour in search of work, during which a person precisely knows what they want. Graduates of this group have a sufficient level of reflection, show independence in finding a job but use little creativity. As a rule, there is an adaptive activity, subject to a definite goal and norms, external conditions.

A separate group of university graduates is creative while looking for work. It is an amateur activity that embraces new, more progressive forms of activity in the employment process. Being by its essence cultural-historical phenomenon, creativity has a psychological aspect: personal and procedural. It presupposes that the individual has abilities, motives, knowledge and skills accordingly, these abilities constructing the new original employment strategies, which are distinguished by novelty and uniqueness. Imagination, intuition, unconscious components of mental activity, as well as the need of the individual for self-actualization, play a crucial role in the development of creative tendencies in the work search.

To study the possibilities of increasing the psychological readiness of university graduates for the employment process, we have developed a programme of psychological support. As a form of psychological influence, the work was aimed at actualisation through the reflection of the resource components of the internal subjective experience of the individual to find the value determinants of development in the employment process.

The main theoretical approaches such as subjective, culturological, competence, humanistic approaches, and such principles as hermeneutic, culturological, meta-principle of humanistic orientation, axiological meta-principle of professional development in the professional sphere are essential for the development of the programme of psychological support in the employment process.

The subjective approach involves the consideration of the personality of the future specialist as a subject of their own professional and personal development, which reveals different attitudes to the world: contemplative, activity, conscious. This vision gives each individual the potential for a reflexive attitude to the world when according to S.L. Rubinstein there is a meaningful outlook on life; every human action reflects their worldview and level of personal freedom [5]. As hermeneutics means "explaining", so adhering to the hermeneutic principle will promote an understanding, a reflexive attitude toward information. In the context of the professional development of future professionals, the hermeneutic meta-principle allows ensuring a high level of awareness of the prospects of their progress, as it will promote the development of professional reflection.

The essence of the competence approach in higher education is to create conditions for future specialists to master various abilities and competencies [6,7]. In our study, the focus is on the professional competence of future professionals, which allows us to talk about the proximity of competency and cultural approaches. In the process of forming multicultural competence of future professionals, it is essential to take into account that the level of human culture is determined not only by whom they are today but also by what they aspire to, what competencies they want to have. According to the culturological meta-principle, one of the unique characteristics of a person with high culture is the ability to continuous self-education and self-development.

In the context of personal and professional development, the meta-principle of humanisation is to take into account the priority values of future professionals, to create favourable conditions for graduates to master social experience, to show their creative individuality and high moral and intellectual qualities [2]. All this will ensure the social security of future workers, as the formation of humanistic values will contribute to greater adaptability to today's working conditions, dictated by the integration of society and the objective logic of the today's world.

The programme of psychological support for university graduates in the employment situation is carried out in three stages: preparatory, motivational-operational, and reflective. Each of the stages has its purpose and content of work, according to which the activities of the coach and graduates take place.

The purpose of the preparatory stage is to equip students with theoretical knowledge about the peculiarities of employment, about the possibilities of self-actualization of the individual within a particular profession. In our opinion, interactive teaching methods should be in use to achieve the goal set at the preparatory stage. After all, the introduction of interactive methods is in dealing with respect for the opinion of students, on the motivation for creativity. As a result, the level of implementation of the principles of consciousness and activity increases [8].

At the motivational-operational stage, the start of independent labour activity created a value attitude to one's own professional development and employment. The motivational-operational step carries on due to the positive motivational involvement of students in the process of forming psychological readiness for employment situation. The progress of positive motivational participation of students, in our opinion, is possible due to training forms of educational activities. Training exercises are beneficial in terms of forming personal motives, because during their implementation "there is figurative modelling of processes that take place in the motivational sphere of man, during the selection and using of definite behavioural strategies. Awareness of motives,

which manifests itself in behaviour, leads to awareness of their motivational vectors and a clearer understanding of the problem situation” [9, p.164].

At the reflexive stage, there are the following changes: a conscious attitude to one’s individuality and professional affiliation form; the reflection on the prospects of one’s professional development develops; and the ability to analyse probabilistic trajectories and possible crises of professional development emerges, and the ability to reflect one’s feelings in different professional situations appears.

In our opinion, it is natural to use reflection training to ensure students’ reflective attitude to their own personal and professional development. As a basis, we chose the training of reflexivity, developed by E. E. Symanyuk, adapting it to the objectives of our study. At the same time, we understand that “reflection is the understanding and knowledge of a person himself and finding out how others know and understand his reactions and cognitive ideas” [10, p.146].

This training promotes the development of communicative and personal reflection, i.e. such a quality that allows you to accept yourself in the profession, to compare their professional qualities with the requirements of work.

Let’s outline the main methodological and theoretical bases of training. First, reflective techniques should be used in the process of forming the psychological readiness of future professionals for the employment process, because the development of reflection is directly related to the development of professional consciousness, which is repeatedly emphasized in the psychological and pedagogical literature [3]. Secondly, a sufficient level of development of reflection is a necessary condition for the effectiveness of the professional activity of a modern worker [11]. Third, it is crucial to keep in mind that the use of reflexive techniques can not directly change human behaviour, also as their effect becomes noticeable only after some time. However, reflection techniques affect the development of personality [12].

Conclusions

The beginning of self-employment is the crucial stage in the process of professional development of future graduates of higher education, the content of which largely depends on the level of professional reflection of graduates, their ability to value-semantic self-determination and the type of values. The study outlined that university graduates may show different attitudes to the employment situation in the form of imaginary desires, specific actions or creative manifestations in search of a job. Due to the manifestations of particular levels of internal activity and self-determination of university graduates in the process of finding a job, we consider it necessary to develop a programme of psychological support for the employment process.

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Prezentat la 14.12.2020